

Arsenic Contamination in Drinking Water: A Case Study in Bilugyun Area, Chaungzon Township, Mon State

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Abstract

The study Bilugyun Area, Chaungzon Township is situated at the bank of Thanlwin River and bounded by latitude between $N16^{\circ}10'$ and $16^{\circ}30'$, longitude between $E 97^{\circ} 37'$ and $97^{\circ}37'$. The purpose of this research is to analyze for the safety drinking water of study area. The water samples from dug wells, tube wells, pond and streams are analyzed for the arsenic contamination by the field test kid method. The 581 water samples of 31 villages from the study area are tested for the arsenic contamination. There are 112ppb of arsenic contamination in drinking water samples from 30' - 45' depth in shallow tube wells from two villages, Da-Uyat (west) and Kawmupon which are situated at the northern part of study area. As a result, this research concluded that possible source of arsenic contamination in study area is shallow tube wells which are situated at younger alluvium deposit of oxbow lake or old river channel because where is more favorable for the arsenic concentration.

Key Words: Arsenic contamination, Drinking water, Bilugyun

Introduction

This research is based on the analysis of arsenic contamination in drinking water of Bilugyun Area. It is important for local people. Because if local people take long term arsenic contaminated water, they will suffer from the arsenicosis disease: thickening of the skin, darker skin, abdominal pain, heart disease and cancer.

Location, Size and Accessibility

The Bilugyun Area, Chaungzon Township is located at the mouth of Thanlwin River. Gulf of Martaban and Adaman Sea are located in the western and southern parts of the study area. The study area is bounded by Latitude between $N16^{\circ} 10'$ and $N16^{\circ} 30'$, Longitude between $E97^{\circ} 27'$ and $E97^{\circ}37'$. The study area can be reached by car through Thanlwin River. The study area can be seen in the following figure (1).

Figure (1) Location Map of Study Area

Topography and Drainage

The topography of the study area can be divided into three parts such as alluvial flat plain, lateritic high ground and central hilly terrain. The central hilly terrain is folded mountain

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ranges and built up metamorphic rock which is trending from north to south. Most of drainage systems of this area are coarse and fine dendritic, rectangular, sub-parallel and radial pattern. Some streams transportation such as the streams, Kahnyaw, Bonet, Kmamo, Kwanyaik, Hpanpha, Htanbingon and Mayan are used for transportation.

Climate

The study area has moderate climate in February, March and April as the continent wind and sea wind simultaneously blow in this time because they come from the Adamen Sea. The annual rain fall of the western part of the study area is above 200 inches and the eastern part is 170 inches. The Rainy season of the study area is from May to October. Average annual temperature is about 64°F in the day time. The highest temperature is in March and April and the lowest temperature in December.

Population

The Bilukyun Island, Chaungzon Township is composed of 64 villages. The population is not homogenous, as significant populations are the Mon, Kayin and Bamar. The rest are Rakhine, Shan and Indian.

Purpose of Study

The main purpose of this study is to analyze for arsenic content in drinking water. And this research is to awareness to local people about arsenic contaminated water which is not suitable for drinking and cooking purpose.

Previous Works

In 1991, Daw Aye Thaug studied the geology of Bilukyan Island for her MSc Degree.

In 2004 and 2019, the arsenic testing program is being carried out in 44 townships based on the existing hydro geological condition and preliminary water quality testing results of the Department of Development Affairs (DDA) and the Water Resources Utilization Department (WRUD).

Method of Study

Arsenic can be tested from water and rock of the study area. Arsenic testing of water has two ways which are laboratory grade and field grade methods. Field grade methods are the one where test kits such as the “arsenator” which is a new instrument for measuring arsenic based on the Gutzeit Method. Present study is used by the field test kit method because the arsenator seems to be the most available. Arsenic concentration can be tested from the slate rock (or) any rocks. In this method, the fine powder of slate rock 1 gram and equaritor acid 10cc are filled in to the test tube and the test tube is heated. This experiment is acid leaching method for arsenic in rock. When these solvent is dried, there will remain as a residual material. These residual material and distilled water 60cc are filled into test tube and then it is tested by arsenic field test kit method. In this experiment, there are various amount of arsenic concentration depending on the amount of residual material and various amount of distilled water.

Analysis on Arsenic contamination in Drinking Water of Bilugyun Area

In 2004 and 2019, the 540 water samples of 25 villages are based on the water quality testing results of the occupational health section of Medical Department and UNICEF (WES section) and the Water Resources Utilization Department (WRUD). In May-2019, the 41 water samples of 6 villages are tested again for this research. The water samples were collected from the water source of dug well, shallow tube well, deep tube well, pond, stream and slate mine.

The arsenic contamination in water Sources of Bilugyun Area show in tables (1and 2) and figure (2).

Table (1) Arsenic Contamination in Water Sources of Bilugyun Area

Sr	Village	Total	Shallow Tube Well			Dug Well			Deep Tubewell			Porid		Stream		
		WS	<50	51-100	>100	Total	<50	>50	Total	<50	>50	Total	<50	Total	>50	Total
1	Chaungzon (west)	14	10			10	4		4							
2	Chaungzon (east)	30	28			28	2		2							
3	Chaungzon Ywathit	23	22			22	1		1							
4	Ywalut	30	11			11	18		18			1	1			
5	Kalwi	18	3			3	15		15							
6	Nyaunglan	16	1			1	15		15							
7	Muyitkyi	24	4			4	20		20							
8	Winsein (Karen)	18					18		18							
9	Kamanin	12					12		12							
10	Muyitkalay	28	8			8	20		20							
11	Hpanhpa	24	6			6	18		18							
12	Kwanthe	18					18		18							
13	Mayan	12	2			2	8		8	2		2				
14	Kalabe	15					15		15							
15	Kamake	40	11			11	29		29							
16	Welan	12					12		12							
17	Kawkadaik	12	2			2	10		10							
18	Da-Ukyat (west)	30	12	11	4	27						3	3			
19	Kawmupun	39	2	13	18	33	2		2			2	2	2	2	2
20	Kahnyaw	30	4			4	25		25			1	1			
21	Bonet	32					32		32							
22	Netmaw	4										4	4			
23	Ywalut (Ywathit)	12	1			1	11		11							
24	Dayal	30	5			5	25		25							
25	Mfudu	14					13		13						1	1
26	Da-Ukyat (east)	4	4			4										
27	Daung-U	4					4		4							
28	Kamamo	4	4			4										
29	Tawkana	3					3		3							
30	Kataungssein	4					4		4							
31	Thetkel	25	11			11	14		14							
		581	151	24	22	197	368		368	2		2	11	11	3	3

■ Arsenic high Contaminated area

Table (2) Arsenic Contamination in Water Sources of Bilugyun Area

Sr. No.	Water Source	Arsenic Concentration		
		<50 µg/L	51-100µg/L	>100 µg/L
1	Shallow tube well	151	24	22
2	Deep tube well	2	0	0
3	Dug well	368	0	0
4	Pond	11	0	0
5	Stream	3	0	0
Total water sample		535	24	22

Figure (2) Arsenic Contamination in Water Sources of Bilugyun Area

Analysis on Arsenic content in Rock and Soil of Bilugyun Area

The arsenic concentration of meta-sedimentary rocks from 8 slate samples of study area were tested by the acid leaching which expressed as the variation of arsenic concentration which depend on the mixed of distilled water amount. The arsenic content in rock and soil of Bilugyun area shows in figure (3).

Figure (3) Arsenic Content in Rock and Soil of Bilugyun Area

Arsenic contamination in Tube well

The highest arsenic contaminated water source is shallow tube well and the underground depth is 45 feet. The highest arsenic contaminated level is 112 µg/l (or) ppb by the testing of field test kit method. By WHO Drinking water Quality standard, the arsenic content 10 ppb (or) 0.01µg/l is risk level for drinking water. The maximum allowed arsenic level in the final draft of the proposed Myanmar Drinking water Quality standard is 50ppb. This is five times higher than WHO recommendation, but still in line with the drinking water standard value of many other regional countries such as China, Bangladesh, Lao and Thailand. The arsenic contamination in tube well of Bilugyun Area show in table (3) and figure (4).

Table (3) Arsenic Contamination in Tube Well of Bilugyun Area

Sr. no.	Depth (ft)	As					Total
		0 µg/L	1-10 µg/L	11-50 µg/L	51-100 µg/L	> 100 µg/L	
1	0-30	230	61	7	2	0	300
2	31-60	104	21	15	19	24	183
3	61-90	48	7	4	2	1	62
4	91-120	16	8	2	0	0	26
5	121-150	6	1	1	0	0	8
6	151-180	1	0	0	0	0	1
7	181-210	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	211-240	1	0	0	0	0	1
Total water sample							581

Generally, groundwater is more vulnerable to the accumulation of high arsenic concentration than surface water because of increased opportunities for chemical reactions between the

ground water and host rocks. Most cases of arsenic concentration in groundwater are related to oxidation and reduction processes in older alluvial aquifer. For these reasons, tube-wells are often more susceptible to arsenic contamination than hand dug-wells surprisingly in Myanmar. Arsenic concentration can be seasonal changed. Thus, the two contaminated villages are tested again for confirming at the date of June, 2019. As a result, there are small variations between two time results.

Figure (4) Arsenic Contamination in Drinking Water of Bilugyun Area

Finding and Discussion

The water samples from dug wells, tube wells, pond and streams are analyzed for the arsenic contamination by the field test kid method. The 581 water samples of 31 villages of the study area are tested for the arsenic contamination. There are 112ppb of arsenic contamination in drinking water samples from 30' - 45' depth in shallow tube wells from two villages, Da-Uyat (west) and Kawmupon where are situated at the northern part of study area. These water contaminated villages are situated on young alluvium deposit of ancient oxbow lake or old river channel. The conditions of arsenic contamination for the study area may be considered as the pyritization (or) arsenopyrite of slate, using the arsenic bearing pesticides and Younger alluvium deposit. Firstly, arsenic concentration of meta-sedimentary rocks from 8 slate samples of study area were tested by the acid leaching which expressed as the variation of arsenic concentration which depend on the mixed of distilled water amount. According to the test results, it is not favorable for the arsenic contamination from arsenopyrite of slate. Secondly, arsenic contamination of drinking water can be caused by using the arsenic bearing pesticides for the rubber plantation areas. But it is unreliable for arsenic contamination to drinking water because although there are many rubber plantations around the whole study area, only the northern part of study area is contaminated in arsenic.

Finally, This research concluded that possible source of arsenic contamination is younger alluvium deposit of oxbow lake or old river channel because the contaminated shallow tube wells locate in younger alluvium deposit of oxbow lake where is more favorable for the arsenic concentration. By image processing techniques, the contaminated area is oxbow lake or old river channel. The satellite image of Bilugyun Area shows in figure (5).

Figure (5) Satellite Image of Bilugyun Area (Path and Row 131_049, Acquisition Date_2020/02/17)

Summary and Conclusion

There are 112ppb of arsenic contamination in drinking water samples from 30' - 45' depth in shallow tube wells from two villages, Da-Uyat (west) and Kawmupon where are situated at the northern part of study area. Finally, this research concluded that the possible source of arsenic contamination in study area is shallow tube wells which are situated at older alluvium deposit of oxbow lake or old river channel because where is more favorable for the arsenic concentration. The tri-pot and transfer water methods should be used for safety drinking from the arsenic contaminated drinking water in study area.

Suggestion for awareness system of Arsenic Contamination

When a well is identified as being contaminated by arsenic, the people who use the well are informed of this fact, and should be warned the dangers of consuming contaminated water for drinking and cooking purposes. In arsenic contaminated water resource area, the native people should be used some ways for drinking and cooking water such as alternative water supply options include rain water harvesting and surface water treatment system.

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